

Province	Species	Statistic	p-value	Province	Species	Statistic	p-value
Andaman	<i>A. akallopisos</i>	6.139	9.99e-04	Sahul Shelf	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	7.203	9.99e-04
Andaman	<i>A. clarkii</i>	2.126	1.38e-01	Somali Arabian	<i>A. clarkii</i>	3.792	6.99e-03
Andaman	<i>A. ephippium</i>	8.134	0e+00	Somali Arabian	<i>A. omanensis</i>	1.356	6.49e-02
Andaman	<i>A. frenatus</i>	18.312	0e+00	South China Sea	<i>A. clarkii</i>	1.316	6.39e-02
Andaman	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	4.292	9.99e-03	South China Sea	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	4.634	0e+00
Andaman	<i>A. sebae</i>	7.131	9.99e-04	South China Sea	<i>A. perideraion</i>	6.873	0e+00
Central Indian Ocean Islands	<i>A. bicinctus</i>	7.563	9.99e-04	South Kuroshio	<i>A. clarkii</i>	1.575	2.64e-01
Central Indian Ocean Islands	<i>A. chagosensis</i>	18.784	0e+00	South Kuroshio	<i>A. frenatus</i>	10.331	0e+00
Central Indian Ocean Islands	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.841	3.36e-01	South Kuroshio	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	8.137	9.99e-04
Central Indian Ocean Islands	<i>A. nigripes</i>	6.094	0e+00	South Kuroshio	<i>A. perideraion</i>	1.774	1.15e-01
Central Polynesia	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	4.696	1.5e-02	Southeast Polynesia	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	7.296	9.99e-04
East Central Australian Shelf	<i>A. akindynos</i>	7.156	9.99e-04	Southeast Polynesia	<i>A. percula</i>	35.481	0e+00
East Central Australian Shelf	<i>A. latezonatus</i>	9.776	0e+00	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. akallopisos</i>	1.883	1.1e-01
East Central Australian Shelf	<i>A. melanopus</i>	0.199	6.61e-01	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.025	9.99e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	9.456	2e-03	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. frenatus</i>	0.809	1.27e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. clarkii</i>	1.540	1.68e-01	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	0.289	5.15e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. leucokranos</i>	14.643	0e+00	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. perideraion</i>	1.177	1.83e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. melanopus</i>	7.578	0e+00	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. polymnus</i>	2.699	4.1e-02
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. percula</i>	1.404	1.33e-01	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. sandaracinos</i>	0.087	8.75e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. perideraion</i>	6.971	3e-03	Sunda Shelf	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	4.038	5.99e-03
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. polymnus</i>	9.192	0e+00	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	0.498	6.32e-01
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. sandaracinos</i>	5.869	0e+00	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	<i>A. clarkii</i>	2.760	5.19e-02
Eastern Coral Triangle	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	7.085	2e-03	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	<i>A. melanopus</i>	3.239	1.1e-02
Java Transitional	<i>A. clarkii</i>	3.166	2.7e-02	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	<i>A. perideraion</i>	0.493	4.81e-01
Java Transitional	<i>A. ephippium</i>	19.274	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. akindynos</i>	0.741	3.55e-01
Java Transitional	<i>A. frenatus</i>	6.443	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. barberi</i>	10.066	0e+00
Java Transitional	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	5.668	2e-03	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	0.634	4.92e-01
Java Transitional	<i>A. perideraion</i>	7.530	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.559	5.54e-01
Java Transitional	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	16.195	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. melanopus</i>	2.711	2.4e-02
Lord Howe and Norfolk Islands	<i>A. mccullochi</i>	18.319	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. percula</i>	0.310	7.17e-01
Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	0.834	4.1e-01	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. perideraion</i>	4.589	5e-03
Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	<i>A. melanopus</i>	9.743	0e+00	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. rubrocinctus</i>	8.953	0e+00
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. akindynos</i>	0.652	5.52e-01	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	<i>A. tricinctus</i>	1.705	1.05e-01
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. chrysopterus</i>	0.356	8.88e-01	Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	<i>A. clarkii</i>	2.113	5.19e-02
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.560	4.99e-01	Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	<i>A. frenatus</i>	22.459	0e+00
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. melanopus</i>	1.498	1.89e-01	West Central Australian Shelf	<i>A. clarkii</i>	13.589	0e+00
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. percula</i>	1.981	9.69e-02	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.415	4.5e-01
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. perideraion</i>	1.650	1.83e-01	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. frenatus</i>	2.955	5e-03
Northeast Australian Shelf	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	4.628	3e-03	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. melanopus</i>	4.070	4e-03
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. clarkii</i>	0.908	3.16e-01	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	0.816	1.87e-01
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. frenatus</i>	11.584	0e+00	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. perideraion</i>	1.903	4.6e-02
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. melanopus</i>	1.345	2.68e-01	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. polymnus</i>	0.557	3.08e-01
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	17.409	0e+00	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. sandaracinos</i>	3.171	5.99e-03
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. perideraion</i>	0.914	3.72e-01	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. sebae</i>	1.646	6.59e-02
Northwest Australian Shelf	<i>A. rubrocinctus</i>	2.591	3.6e-02	Western Coral Triangle	<i>A. biaculeatus</i>	2.204	1.6e-02
Red Sea and Gulf of Aden	<i>A. bicinctus</i>	1.105	2.15e-01	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. akallopisos</i>	1.736	4.1e-02
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. akindynos</i>	2.531	1.3e-02	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. allardi</i>	0.907	1.67e-01
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. clarkii</i>	4.274	1.5e-02	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. chrysogaster</i>	1.205	1.54e-01
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. melanopus</i>	2.662	1.4e-02	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. clarkii</i>	2.906	5.49e-02
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. ocellaris</i>	7.737	0e+00	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. fuscocaudatus</i>	2.740	5e-03
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. perideraion</i>	0.085	8.7e-01	Western Indian Ocean	<i>A. latifasciatus</i>	9.371	0e+00
Sahul Shelf	<i>A. rubrocinctus</i>	0.965	1.19e-01				